

Bioactive Atomic Layer Deposition of TiO₂ on Polyetheretherketone

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Abstract: Structure and functionality of surfaces play a paramount role in a variety of medical applications and are therefore ultimately crucial for the health of the patient, for example after surgery. Prominent examples are the ingrowth behaviour and biocompatibility of implants. TiO₂ thin films were deposited on the orthopedic implant material polyetheretherketone (PEEK) by plasma enhanced atomic layer deposition (PEALD) and characterized for their ability to enhance the osseointegrative properties. The results reveal that the osteogenic properties of the TiO₂ thin film are comparable to those of hydroxyapatite, and thus bioactive properties of PEEK implants are improved by TiO₂ thin films deposited with PEALD. This paper summarises the most important results of a publication of Blendingner et al. in the journal ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces [1].

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I. Introduction

Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) is a semicrystalline polyaromatic linear polymer. The chemical structure makes it resistant to all chemicals apart from sulfuric acid. In contrast to PEEK, titanium as a favoured material for orthopedic implants due to its excellent biocompatibility has a relatively high elastic modulus, 10–20 times greater than that of human bone. This mismatch of the elastic moduli may cause implant loosening or even implantation failure due to stress-shielding on the periimplant bone. Due to its chemical resistance, PEEK is rather a bioinert material, not allowing protein absorption and promotion of cell adhesion. These aspects however play an important role for a successful outcome of implantation and a fast ingrowth process (osseointegration), which are strongly dependent upon the surface characteristics, including roughness, wettability, and chemical composition. Therefore, to improve the biocompatibility of PEEK without sacrificing its excellent bulk properties, one approach is to deposit a coating such as titanium on it. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) builds up as a selfpassivating layer on Ti with a thickness of 2–5 nm and provides corrosion resistance and good osseointegrative properties. Improved osseointegrative properties of PEEK by TiO₂ deposition have already been observed. Multiple methods exist for the deposition of Ti and TiO₂ at moderate temperatures, applicable for temperature-sensitive substrates like polymers. Implant surfaces typically feature a micron-scale roughness, enhancing osteoblast differentiation and increasing the bone-implant contact rate in vivo as well as improving the interlocking between mineralized bone and the implant surface. In this case, not every deposition method leads to the desired properties of a uniform coating.

The coating of complex shaped implants can lead to noncoated areas due to shadowing effects. A promising technique to deposit homogeneous and defect-free coatings even on complex surfaces is atomic layer deposition

(ALD).

I.1. Plasma enhanced atomic layer deposition

Atomic layer deposition (ALD) is a thin-film deposition technique with self-terminating reaction sequences between vapor-phase precursors and the growth surface with a high control over the thickness in the atomic regime. Therefore, it is suitable for deposition of uniform and conformal coatings on complex three-dimensional structures. However, the deposition temperatures used in these studies typically exceeded the glass transition temperature of PEEK (145 °C). Thus, these processes are not applicable to PEEK. Addressing temperature-sensitive materials like PEEK, plasma enhanced ALD (PEALD) allows for deposition at lower temperatures by use of oxygen plasma instead of water for typical oxide deposition processes (**Fig. 1**).

Figure 1: Schematic of the remote PEALD reactor.

Using a remote plasma source by separating the plasma source and the substrate by a grid reduces the ion bombardment, but maintains the flow of radicals to the substrate surface. Improved conformality by use of such a plasma source was already shown for TiO₂ deposited with PEALD on microscopic test structures. In our study, we

have chosen a macroscopic test structure for conformality measurements, with the dimensions of the test structure resembling roughly the dimensions of an orthopedic implant for spinal fusion.

II. Material and methods

Atomic layer deposition was carried out using a “MyPlas” PEALD (Plasma Electronic GmbH, Germany) in a remote plasma configuration with a 13.56 MHz capacitively coupled plasma (CCP) source and a substrate holder with an area of $100 \times 100 \text{ mm}^2$. The schematic of the reactor is shown in Figure 1. In order to have a sufficiently large volume for deposition onto 3D objects with a remote plasma configuration, TiO_2 thin films were deposited using titanium(IV)isopropoxide [$\text{Ti}(\text{OCH}(\text{CH}_3)_2)_4$, TTIP, >97%] (abr GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) and oxygen. Argon was used as a purging gas after each ALD step. The substrate temperature was held at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and TTIP was heated to $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to obtain a sufficiently high vapor pressure. To prevent vapor condensation, the TTIP precursor valves were heated to $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and vapor delivery lines were held at $95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Flow rates of oxygen gas and plasma gas delivery were set to 13 sccm and argon gas flow, used for purging of the precursor delivery line after the precursor step, to 6 sccm using separate mass flow controllers (MFCs). Pressure during plasma operation was monitored with a capacitance pressure sensor (Baratron, MKS) and did not exceed 5 Pa. Film growth was monitored in situ with a quartz-crystal microbalance next to the substrate holder. PEEK samples (Invibio) consisted of circular disks with 15 mm diameter that were grit-blasted and cleaned in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min in acetone, isopropanol, and deionized (DI) water. Prior to film deposition, the PEEK substrates were plasma-treated in the PEALD with oxygen plasma at 150 W RF power and 20 sccm O_2 gas flow for 5 min.

III. Results and discussion

Film Morphology

TiO_2 films with approx. 50 nm thickness were deposited on 100-Si wafers and PEEK samples. PEEK samples were examined with FIB-SEM (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: SEM micrograph of FIB cut through grit-blasted and TiO_2 -coated PEEK. The PEEK substrate is visible on the right-hand side of the image (dark gray). A homogeneous coating even in trench-like structures is visible by a slightly lighter coloured layer on top of the PEEK surface.

Biocompatibility

Biocompatibility was measured against BCP as a reference material known to support good cell adhesion, with quantitative values above 80% of those for the reference material considered as an indication of good biocompatibility. After 48 h of cultivation, the cell number was determined by the amount of total DNA from cells that were attached to the surface and not removed through washing steps. The amount of DNA retrieved from the TiO_2 -coated PEEK and BCP is approximately the same within the error margin, with a slightly larger variation on the TiO_2 -coated PEEK. These results indicate that the TiO_2 -coated PEEK is fully biocompatible and cell growth and cell activity are supported equally well compared to BCP. Furthermore, cell spreading was verified by SEM on samples cultivated for 48 h.

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